

Restaurant Efficiency in Venturing Online Food Delivery Services in Alaminos City During Pandemic

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ABSTRACT: Online food delivery has made a major impact on the restaurant industry during the Covid-19 pandemic. Most traditional restaurants have ventured into online food delivery. This study was conducted to assess the effectiveness and efficiency rate of restaurants in Alaminos, venturing into an Online Food Delivery Services amidst the pandemic. The study used survey questionnaires using google forms to collect data. Frequency counts, percentage, weighted mean and analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine the significant difference between the strategies used across profile variables were used. A total of 300 managers and employees serve as the respondents of the study. Results showed that 181 or 60.3% of the respondents exist within the bracket of one (1) to five (5) years in the food business, strategically located within Poblacion area of Alaminos City and have collaborations with food riders. That the effect of the used strategies in the implementation of online food delivery service has a huge impact on the overall operations of the Restaurants, Cafés, and Milk tea shops. That “establishment offering deals such as promos, combos, and holiday promos”, has a significant difference to the profile variables in terms of the years of existence, strategic location and type of establishment.

KEYWORDS: Restaurant, online food delivery, pandemic, food establishment, café

INTRODUCTION

At present, the COVID-19 Pandemic dramatically affects the world, especially the substantial growth and investment of state and local governments in the tourism and hospitality industries. As a result, establishments, organizations, and businesses are being stopped with their operations. Still, none has been severely affected as the hospitality industry. Specifically, the hotels, restaurants, tourist attractions, conference and convention venues, cruise lines, airlines, travel agencies, tour operators, to name just a few, ceased to operate or curtailed their operation to a fraction of their capacity. The Restaurant Industry is hugely at risk because most of the establishments and enterprises have closed because of the implementation of lockdown. Because of this, many employees and workers in the hospitality industry are significantly affected. Furthermore, the Restaurants' growth mechanism and profit development are also at risk and probably downgraded.

Restaurant owners worldwide who compete to capture new customers have already jumped on the online delivery trend. People have moved from ordering offline to ordering online because it is easy, convenient, and transparent. They can finally say goodbye to the hustle and bustle generated by the old ways of food ordering. Consumers wanted convenience in all aspects of their lives, including food. In the new COVID-19 world, that demand for food convenience has increased – both by necessity (i.e., shelter-in-place orders) and because so many brands are jumping on the online food delivery service. To make this service available to customers, restaurants rely on third-party delivery providers or create their own with an online ordering system.

Food delivery has already made a significant impact on the restaurant industry. It's even inspired a whole new category of restaurant, which are restaurants that offers food via delivery. And because of the threat of COVID-19 Pandemic, traditional restaurants have ventured into an Online food delivery that focuses on food preparation and order fulfillment rather than an experience. Since most dining rooms have been forced to close at some point in the past few months, Restaurants that venture into online food delivery have had their time to shine, helping diners get their favorite dishes safely and lowering operational costs for restaurant owners.

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Experts predict that the Pandemic will accelerate the creation of ghost kitchens across the country to give restaurants a more sustainable business model and meet the high demand for takeout and delivery from consumers (Last name, date; Last name, date). That being said, Carryout and Online food delivery service as the new normal for the Restaurant Service.

In this regard, the researchers aim to conduct a study to assess the effectiveness and efficiency rate of Restaurants here in Alaminos venturing into an Online Food Delivery Service amidst the Pandemic. The researchers will be conducting the study in some Restaurants here in Alaminos City because they are aware that the business establishments here in Alaminos City have ceased or curtailed their operation because of the COVID-19 Pandemic. The researchers will also be conducting the study, particularly in some well-known Restaurants in Alaminos City because, according to the report, big establishments, including hotels and restaurants, have been severely impacted by the Covid-19 Pandemic. Moreover, the researchers are trying to figure out the possible advantages and disadvantages of Restaurant Efficiency venturing into Online Food Delivery services and the potential effects of new normal set up to know how it affects the operating system. Lastly, this will benefit all restaurant owners and entrepreneurs to be more aware and knowledgeable about the effectiveness and efficiency rate of merging and venturing out to Online Food Delivery Services amidst the threat of the Covid-19 Pandemic.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness and efficiency of the Restaurants venturing in online food delivering service in Alaminos City. The study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the food establishment in terms of the following:
 - a. Years of existence
 - b. Strategic location
 - c. Type of Establishment
2. What are the common strategies used in Online Food Delivery services?
3. What are the effects of the used strategies in implementing Online Food Delivery in Restaurants during the Pandemic?
4. What are the problems encountered by the establishment venturing online food services?
5. Is there a significant difference between the strategies used across profile variables?

The null hypothesis of this study was tested at 0.5 level of significance:

There is no significant relationship between the level of satisfaction on online payment and the profile of the online buyers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The mix – method type of research was used in the study. In this design, researchers will gather quantitative data first, and qualitative data will follow it. The subjects of the study are 20 well known Restaurant's with a sample size of 300 respondents. The study was conducted in Alaminos City. The respondents were the employees, owners and managers of the Café's and Restaurant's who ventures in online food delivery service. The data gathering instrument used was a survey questionnaire through Google Forms that was constructed by the researchers and validated by five experts. Several statistical tools such as percentages, frequency counts, weighted mean, and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used in the statistical treatment of data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As shown in Table I A, in the year bracket, respondents between 1 - 5 years have a frequency count of 181, equivalent to 60.3 percent. In the year bracket of existence, between 6 to 10 years have a frequency count of 45, equal to 15 percent. In comparison, in the year bracket of existence between 16 to 20 years have a frequency count of 31, which is equivalent to 10.3 percent, and in the year bracket of 11 months and below have a frequency count of 24, which is equal to 8 percent. And the lowest year bracket of the existence of the respondents belongs to 11 to 15 years which has a frequency count of 19 and is equivalent to 6.3 percent.

Years of Existence		
	Frequency	Percent
11monthsbelow	24	8.0
1 to 5 years	181	60.3
6 to 10 years	45	15.0
11 to 15 years	19	6.3
16 to 20 years	31	10.3
Total	300	100.0

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	Frequency	Percent
<u>Bued</u>	12	4.0
<u>Lucap</u>	73	24.3
<u>Palamis</u>	48	16.0
<u>Poblacion</u>	117	39.0
<u>Tanaytay</u>	50	16.7
Total	300	100.0

As shown in Table I. B, in terms of the strategic location of the respondents, Poblacion Alaminos City Pangasinan has the highest frequency count of 117, which is equivalent to 39 percent, and in the location of Lucap Alaminos City Pangasinan has a frequency count of 73 which is equal to 24.3 percent. In comparison, in the location of Tanaytay, Alaminos City Pangasinan have a frequency count of 50, which is equivalent to 16.7 percent. In the location of Palamis, Alaminos City Pangasinan gathered a frequency count of 48, which is equivalent to 16 percent. Bued, Alaminos City, has the lowest frequency count of 12, equal to 4 percent.

	Frequency	Percent
<u>Café</u>	46	15.3
<u>MilkTea Shop</u>	54	18.0
<u>Restaurant</u>	200	66.7
Total	300	100.0

As shown in Table I. C, in terms of the type of establishment of the respondents, Restaurants have the highest frequency count of 200, which is equivalent to 66.7 percent, next are the Milk Tea Shops, which have a frequency count of 54 that is equivalent to 18 percent.

Table 2. Common Strategies used in online food delivery service

	Descriptive Statistics				
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Strategies-1	300	2	5	3.93	1.136
Strategies-2	300	3	5	4.72	.457
Strategies-3	300	2	5	4.92	.332
Strategies-4	300	1	5	2.77	1.352
Strategies-5	300	1	5	3.84	1.050
Strategies-6	300	1	5	3.12	1.220
Strategies-7	300	1	5	4.35	.989
Strategies-8	300	3	5	4.67	.499
Strategies-9	300	3	5	4.49	.696
Strategies-10	300	3	5	4.65	.485
Strategies-11	300	1	5	3.46	1.219
Strategies-12	300	1	5	3.39	1.239
Valid N (list wise)	300				

Legend: 1.0-1.75 Less Effective

1.76-2.49 Slightly Effective

2.50-3.24 Effective

3.25-4.0 Moderately Effective

4.01-5.0 Highly Effective

Table 2 presents the Restaurants' common strategies in Alaminos venturing into an Online Food Delivery Service. The data shows the number of respondents, frequency count, minimum and maximum scale, weighted mean, and the standard deviation.

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Based on the data gathered by the researchers as reflected in Table 2, Strategy number 3, "The Establishments has collaborations with food riders." got the highest weighted mean of 4.92. In contrast, the second-highest belongs to Strategy number 2, "The Establishments cellular applications is often used," which has an average weighted mean of 4.72, the third-highest is Strategy number 8, "The establishment is offering discounts and deals" with an average weighted mean of 4.67, the fourth highest strategy is number 10, "The establishment is offering deals such as promos, combos and holiday promos" which has an average weighted mean of 4.65 and the fifth-highest strategy belongs to number 9 "The establishment offer rewards, referral, and feedbacks" with an average weighted mean of 4.49. The top five strategies correspond to Highly Effective and commonly used strategies by the Restaurants, Café, and Milk Tea Shops establishments. While Strategy number 4, "The establishments is in collaborations with food bloggers," got the lowest weighted mean of 2.77.

Table 3. Effects of the used strategies in the implementation of online food delivery service in Restaurants during pandemic

		Statistics				
		Effects of Strategies-1	Effects of Strategies-2	Effects of Strategies-3	Effects of Strategies-4	Effects of Strategies-5
N	Valid	300	300	300	300	300
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
	Mean	3.96	4.38	4.88	4.78	2.24
	Std. Deviation	1.149	.806	.411	.444	1.222
	Minimum	2	2	2	3	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5

*Legend: 1.0-1.75 Never Practice
1.76-2.49 Slightly Practice
2.50-3.24 Practice
3.25-4.0 Moderately Practice
4.01-5.0 Highly Practice*

Based on the data gathered by the researchers as reflected in Table 3, Effect number 3, "Clients/Customers prefer to order our promo food products," got the highest weighted mean of 4.88, the second-highest is Effect number 4, "Clients/Customers prefer to order our combo meals using their rewards" which have an average weighted mean of 4.78, the third-highest is Effect number 2 which is "Clients/Customers prefer to call our cellular phones or landline" and got an average weighted mean of 4.38. The top three (3) effects of the used strategy are interpreted as Highly Practice. Effect number 1, "Clients/Customers prefer to use our online website," got an average weighted mean of 3.96 and was interpreted as Moderately Practice. In contrast, Effect number 5, "Clients/Customers prefer to pick their orders in the market meet up," got the lowest weighted mean of 2.24 and was interpreted as Slightly Practice.

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Table 4. Problems encountered by the establishments venturing into online food delivery services

		Statistics									
		Problem 1	Problem 2	Problem 3	Problem 4	Problem 5	Problem 6	Problem 7	Problem 8	Problem 9	Problem 10
N	Valid	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mean	2.51	2.31	3.63	2.19	1.95	3.67	1.72	1.98	1.45	4.23
	Std. Deviation	1.343	1.283	1.395	1.242	1.218	1.457	.794	1.307	.639	1.192
	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	4	5

*Legend: 1.0-1.75 Never
1.76-2.49 Seldom
2.50-3.24 Sometimes
3.25-4.0 Often
4.01-5.0 Always*

Based on the data gathered by the researchers as reflected in Table 4. Problem number 10, "Shifting of customers preference," got the highest weighted mean of 4.23 and was interpreted as an Always encountered problem by the establishments. At the same time, the second-highest belongs to Problem number 6, "Unstable Market Price due to insufficient supplies," which has an average weighted mean of 3.67 and is interpreted as Often encountered problems by the establishment, the third-highest is Problem number 3, "Higher labor cost due to lesser order" with an average weighted mean of 3.63 which is also interpreted as an Often encountered problem by the establishments, the fourth-highest problem is number 1, "Abrupt cancellation of orders made by the customers" which has an average weighted mean of 2.51 and interpreted as Sometimes encountered problem by the establishments. In contrast, the fifth-highest problem is number 2, "Improper handling of food by the riders," with an average weighted mean of 2.31, which the establishments Seldom encounter. While the Never encountered problem and the lowest average weighted mean of 1.45 belong to Problem number 9, which is the "Lack of chef or cook in the restaurant."

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Table 5. A Strategy 3: Significance difference across profile variables

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Strategies-3						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	6.570 ^a	11	.597	6.529	.000	.200
Intercept	3657.593	1	3657.593	39982.145	0.000	.993
Years of Existence	1.651	4	.413	4.512	.001	.059
Strategic Location	3.622	4	.906	9.899	.000	.121
Type of Establishment	.659	2	.329	3.601	.029	.024
Years of Existence * Strategic Location	0.000	0				0.000
Years of Existence * Type of Establishment	0.000	0				0.000
Strategic Location * Type of Establishment	0.000	0				0.000
Years of Existence * Strategic Location * Type of Establishment	0.000	0				0.000
Error	26.346	288	.091			
Total	7285.000	300				
Corrected Total	32.917	299				

Under strategy number 3, "The Establishments has collaborations with food riders," there is a .034 significant difference in terms of Years of Existence which occurred in 16 to 20 years versus 6 to 10 years and vice versa and also has a significant difference to their average mean score. Regarding strategic location in strategy number 3, there is a .022 significant difference between Lucap Alaminos City Pangasinan versus Poblacion Alaminos City Pangasinan and vice versa. There is also a .002 significant difference between Palamis Alaminos City Pangasinan versus Poblacion Alaminos City Pangasinan and in Poblacion Alaminos City Pangasinan there is a significant difference between Lucap and Palamis Alaminos City Pangasinan and also has a .001 significant difference between Poblacion and Tanaytay Alaminos City Pangasinan and vice versa while in terms of the Type of Establishment by the respondents under the strategy number 3, Milk Tea Shop versus Restaurant and vice versa has a .023 significant difference. Therefore, there is a significant effect and difference of the mean score of strategy number 3 in terms of the profile variables of the respondents.

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Table 5. B Strategy 2: Significance difference across profile variables

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects					
Dependent Variable: Strategies-2					
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	44.420 ^a	11	4.038	64.399	.000
Intercept	3405.957	1	3405.957	54315.703	0.000
Years of Existence	2.299	4	.575	9.168	.000
Strategic Location	21.372	4	5.343	85.205	.000
Type of Establishment	.631	2	.315	5.029	.007
Years of Existence * Strategic Location	0.000	0			
Years of Existence * Type of Establishment	0.000	0			
Strategic Location * Type of Establishment	0.000	0			
Years of Existence * Strategic Location * Type of Establishment	0.000	0			
Error	18.060	288	.063		
Total	6746.000	300			
Corrected Total	62.480	299			

Under strategy number 2, "The establishments cellular applications are often used," there is a significant difference in terms of years of existence of the respondents in 1 to 5 years versus 11 months below and vice versa there is .004 significant difference while 1 to 5 years versus 11 to 15 years and vice versa there is .013 significant difference. In 1 to 5 years versus 16 to 20 years and vice versa there is a .000 significant difference. In 11 months below versus 16 to 20 years and vice versa, there are .000 significant differences, while in 11 months below versus 6 to 10 years and vice versa, there are .090 significant differences. In 11 to 15 years versus 16 to 20 years and vice versa there are .000 significant differences. In 16 to 20 years versus 6 to 10 years there are .000 significant differences. In terms of strategic location in strategy number 2, there are .000 significant differences between Bued Alaminos City Pangasinan versus Lucap Alaminos City Pangasinan and vice versa, and also in Lucap Alaminos City Pangasinan versus Palamis, Poblacion, Tanaytay Alaminos City Pangasinan and vice versa. In Palamis Alaminos City Pangasinan versus Tanaytay Alaminos City Pangasinan and vice versa and in Poblacion Alaminos City Pangasinan versus Palamis Alaminos City Pangasinan and vice versa there is .007 significant differences. In Poblacion Alaminos City Pangasinan versus Tanaytay Alaminos City Pangasinan and vice versa, .006 significant differences also significantly affect their average mean score. At the same time, in the type of establishment in strategy number 2, there is a .056 significant difference between Café versus Milk tea shop and a .000 significant differences in Café and Restaurant and Milk Tea shop versus restaurant and vice versa. Therefore, there is a significant effect and difference of the mean score of strategy number 2 in terms of the profile variables of the respondents.

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Table 5. C Strategy 8: Significance difference across profile variables

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Strategies-8						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	50.638 ^a	11	4.603	55.960	.000	.681
Intercept	3315.714	1	3315.714	40305.891	0.000	.993
Years of Existence	5.273	4	1.318	16.024	.000	.182
Strategic Location	26.380	4	6.595	80.168	.000	.527
Type of Establishment	2.217	2	1.109	13.477	.000	.086
Years of Existence * Strategic Location	0.000	0				0.000
Years of Existence * Type of Establishment	0.000	0				0.000
Strategic Location * Type of Establishment	0.000	0				0.000
Years of Existence * Strategic Location * Type of Establishment	0.000	0				0.000
Error	23.692	288	.082			
Total	6617.000	300				
Corrected Total	74.330	299				

Under strategy number 8, "The establishments offering discount and deals," there are .001 significant differences in terms of years of existence between 1 to 5 years versus 11 months below and vice versa. In 1 to 5 years versus 11 to 15 years and vice versa there are .003 significant differences. In 1 to 5 years versus 16 to 20 years and vice versa, and 11 months versus 16 to 20 years and vice versa, there are .000 significant differences. In 11 months versus 6 to 10 years and vice versa, there are .002 significant differences. In 11 to 15 years versus 16 to 20 years and vice versa, there are .000 significant differences, while 11 to 15 years versus 6 to 10 years and vice versa, there are .006 significant differences. In 16 to 20 years versus 6 to 10 years and vice versa there are .000 significant differences. In terms of the strategic location of the respondents under the strategy number 8, Bued Alaminos City Pangasinan versus Lucap Alaminos City Pangasinan and vice versa, in Lucap Alaminos City Pangasinan versus Bued, Palamis, Poblacion and Tanaytay and vice versa, and in Palamis Alaminos City Pangasinan versus Poblacion Alaminos City Pangasinan and vice versa together with Poblacion Alaminos City Pangasinan versus Tanaytay Alaminos City Pangasinan and vice versa there is .000 significant differences. Under the profile variable in terms of the type of establishment of the respondents in café versus milk tea shop and vice versa, there are .000 significant differences while in café versus restaurant and vice versa there is .044 significant differences also has a significant difference to their average mean score. Therefore, there is a significant effect and difference of the mean score of strategy number 8 in terms of the profile variables of the respondents.

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Table 5. D Strategy 10: Significance difference across profile variables

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Strategies-10						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	48.322 ^a	11	4.393	57.695	.000	.688
Intercept	3454.633	1	3454.633	45372.208	0.000	.994
Years of Existence	1.099	4	.275	3.609	.007	.048
Strategic Location	23.252	4	5.813	76.345	.000	.515
Type of Establishment	8.514	2	4.257	55.912	.000	.280
Years of Existence * Strategic Location	0.000	0				0.000
Years of Existence * Type of Establishment	0.000	0				0.000
Strategic Location * Type of Establishment	0.000	0				0.000
Years of Existence * Strategic Location * Type of Establishment	0.000	0				0.000
Error	21.928	288	.076			
Total	6557.000	300				
Corrected Total	70.250	299				

Under strategy number 10, "The establishments are offering deals such as promos, combos, and holiday promos," in terms of years of existence under the 1 to 5 years versus 11 months below, 11 to 15 years and 16 to 20 years has a .000 significant difference while 1 to 5 years versus 6 to 10 years there is .009 significant difference. In 11 months below versus 16 to 20 years and vice versa, there are .000 significant differences, while in 11 months below versus 6 to 10 years, there are .031 significant differences. In 11 to 15 years versus 16 to 20 years and vice versa, there are .000 significant differences, while in 11 to 15 years versus 6 to 10 years and vice versa, there are .062 significant differences. In 16 to 20 years versus 6 to 10 years and vice versa, there are .000 significant differences and a significant difference to their average mean score. Regarding strategic location in strategy number 10, there are .000 significant differences between Bued Alaminos City Pangasinan versus Lucap and Poblacion Alaminos City Pangasinan. In contrast, in terms of the type of establishment in strategy number 10, under café versus milk tea shop and vice versa, there is a .000 significant difference. In contrast, in café versus restaurant and vice versa, there are .009 significant differences. In milk tea shop versus restaurant and vice versa, there are .044 significant differences. Therefore, there is a significant effect and contrast of the mean score of strategy number 10 in terms of the profile variables of the respondents.

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Table 5. E Strategy 9: Significance difference across profile variables

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Strategies-8						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	50.638 ^a	11	4.603	55.960	.000	.681
Intercept	3315.714	1	3315.714	40305.891	0.000	.993
Years of Existence	5.273	4	1.318	16.024	.000	.182
Strategic Location	26.380	4	6.595	80.168	.000	.527
Type of Establishment	2.217	2	1.109	13.477	.000	.086
Years of Existence * Strategic Location	0.000	0				0.000
Years of Existence * Type of Establishment	0.000	0				0.000
Strategic Location * Type of Establishment	0.000	0				0.000
Years of Existence * Strategic Location * Type of Establishment	0.000	0				0.000
Error	23.692	288	.082			
Total	6617.000	300				
Corrected Total	74.330	299				

Under strategy number 9, "The establishments offer rewards, referral, and feedbacks," there is a .000 significant difference in terms of years of existence in 1 to 5 years versus 11 months below, 11 to 15 years, and 16 to 20 years. And also, in 11 months below versus 16 to 20 years and vice versa, there are .000 significant differences, while in 11 months below versus 6 to 10 years and vice versa, there are .007 significant differences. In 11 to 15 years versus 16 to 20 years and vice versa, there are .000 significant differences, while in 11 to 15 years versus 6 to 10 years and vice versa, there are .018 significant differences. In 16 to 20 years versus 6 to 10 years and vice versa there are .000 significant differences. Regarding strategic location in strategy number 9, there are .000 significant differences between Bued Alaminos City Pangasinan versus Lucap Alaminos City Pangasinan and vice versa. Also, in Lucap Alaminos City Pangasinan versus Palamis, Poblacion and Tanaytay and In Poblacion Alaminos City Pangasinan versus Lucap and Palamis Alaminos City Pangasinan have .000 significant differences and also has a significant difference to their average mean score. In contrast, in the type of establishment under strategy number 9, there is a .000 significant difference between café versus restaurant and vice versa and in milk tea shop versus restaurant and vice versa. Therefore, there is a significant effect and difference of the mean score of strategy number 9 in terms of the profile variables of the respondents.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the result of the study that was conducted, the researchers concluded the following:

1. Most of the respondent's existence belongs to the year bracket of 1 to 5 years. The majority of its strategic location came from Poblacion Alaminos City Pangasinan, and most of the respondents were working in the Restaurants establishment.
2. The commonly used strategies by the Restaurants in Alaminos who ventures into an Online Food Delivery Service was strategy number three, "The Establishments has a collaboration with food riders," strategy number two, "The Establishments cellular applications are often used," strategy eighth, "The establishment is offering discounts and deals, Strategy ten, "The establishment is offering deals such as promos, combos, and holiday promos and strategy nine, "The establishment offer rewards, referral and feedbacks: and was interpreted as highly effective strategies used by the Restaurants, Cafes, and Milk Tea Shops.

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3. The effects of the used strategies in the implementation of online food delivery service has a huge impact on the overall operations of the Restaurants, Cafés, and Milk Tea Shop establishments, and the top three effects were recognized as effect number three “Clients/Customers prefer to order our promo food products,” effect number four “Clients/Customers prefer to order our combo meals using their rewards,” effect number two “Clients/Customers prefer to call our cellular phones or landline,” and this was interpreted as highly practice effects of strategies used by the establishments in the implementation of online food delivery service.

4. The degree of seriousness and the level of encountering the online food delivery service problems was recognized in problem number ten, which is the “Shifting of customer’s preference.”

5. There are five strategies which are the strategy number three, “The Establishments has a collaboration with food riders,” strategy number two, “The Establishments cellular applications are often used,” strategy eighth, “The establishment is offering discounts and deals, Strategy ten, “The establishment is offering deals such as promos, combos, and holiday promos and strategy nine, “The establishment offer rewards, referral and feedbacks which has significant effect to the profile variables of the respondents in terms their year of existence, strategic location and type of establishment.

The following recommendations formulated by the researchers are hereby forwarded:

1. Other Café’s and Restaurant’s Establishment and Small Medium Enterprises: They may use this research study to know how the most used strategies in implementing online food delivery services are effective for their respective businesses and how this strategy affects the overall service and operation of a specific establishment.
2. The Café’s and Restaurant’s Owners and Entrepreneurs who venture into Online Food Delivery Service: They must further flourish and boost their strategy to reach higher target customers and meet their customers’ demand and expectation towards delivering quality service.
3. Stakeholders: They may use this research study to know how effective and efficient the strategies used by the Café and Restaurants that venture into online food delivery service and how the implications of the strategy affect the overall service of food delivery.
4. Hospitality Management Students: They may use this research to further gain ideas in planning and applying the most effective strategies by the Café and Restaurants. They venture into online food delivery services.
5. Future Researchers: The researchers highly recommend this research to further use this paper as their basis and support for their future research plans.

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